

CARDIOPROTECTIVE EFFECTS OF GREEN TEA AND OMEGA-3 AGAINST ALUMINUM CHLORIDE-INDUCED CARDIOTOXICITY IN RABBITS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Aluminium chloride ($AlCl_3$) is a widely used inorganic compound known to induce systemic toxicity, especially affecting the cardiovascular system. Chronic exposure to $AlCl_3$ promotes oxidative stress, myocardial degeneration, and biochemical disturbances that impair cardiac function. Natural antioxidants such as green tea polyphenols and omega-3 fatty acids have shown potential protective roles due to their anti-inflammatory and free radical scavenging properties. This study evaluates the cardioprotective effects of green tea and omega-3 against $AlCl_3$ -induced cardiotoxicity in rabbits.

Methods: Thirty-two adult rabbits were divided equally into four groups (n=8). Group I served as the control. Group II received $AlCl_3$ (300 mg/kg/day) orally for 30 days. Group III received $AlCl_3$ with green tea extract (50 mg/kg/day). Group IV received $AlCl_3$ with omega-3 (20 mg/kg/day). Body weight, heart weight, cardiac enzymes (CK-MB, SGOT/AST), and histopathology of cardiac tissue were evaluated. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA.

Results: $AlCl_3$ administration caused significant reductions in body weight and increases in absolute and relative heart weight, indicating hypertrophy. CK-MB and AST levels increased sharply, confirming myocardial injury. Co-treatment with green tea lowered these parameters moderately, while omega-3 supplementation showed **superior protective effects**, restoring cardiac biomarkers close to control values. Histopathological analysis revealed severe myofibrillar degeneration, necrosis, edema, and fibrosis in the $AlCl_3$ group, while green tea reduced these changes and omega-3 preserved near-normal myocardial architecture.

Conclusion: Both green tea and omega-3 exert protective effects against $AlCl_3$ -induced cardiotoxicity, with omega-3 showing greater efficacy. These findings support the potential use of natural antioxidants as therapeutic agents against chemical-induced cardiac injury.

Keywords: Aluminium chloride, Cardiotoxicity, Green tea, Omega-3 fatty acids, Antioxidants, Rabbits, Cardiac biomarkers, Histopathology

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) represent the leading global cause of morbidity and mortality, accounting for 17.9 million deaths annually, with low- and middle-income countries disproportionately affected (WHO, 2023). Pakistan experiences an alarming rise in CVD prevalence, with nearly 29% of national

mortality attributed to cardiac conditions (PHRC, 2022). Rapid urbanization, sedentary lifestyles, hypertension, diabetes, obesity, and environmental pollutants further intensify the burden (Jafar et al., 2021). While multiple risk factors contribute to CVD progression, emerging evidence points to the role of heavy

metals—especially aluminium—as critical but often overlooked contributors to cardiovascular pathology (Nawrot et al., 2011).

Aluminium chloride (AlCl_3), an industrially significant compound used in catalysis, metal processing, pharmaceuticals, and water purification, possesses strong Lewis acid properties and readily hydrolyzes to release reactive species (Fringuelli, 2001). Chronic exposure occurs through contaminated food, water, cosmetics, cookware, and occupational settings (Krewski et al., 2007). Although gastrointestinal absorption of aluminium is limited, factors such as low pH, dietary citrate, and renal impairment enhance systemic uptake (Savory et al., 1996). Aluminium crosses biological barriers and accumulates in soft tissues—including the heart—where it disrupts antioxidant systems, increases ROS formation, alters calcium homeostasis, and induces apoptosis (Jomova et al., 2023).

Cardiac toxicity from aluminium exposure is well documented and includes myocardial necrosis, interstitial edema, inflammation, elevated serum CK-MB and LDH, oxidative stress, mitochondrial swelling, myofibrillar disruption, and induction of pro-apoptotic pathways (Saad et al., 2018; Novaes et al., 2018). These pathological changes align with broader evidence linking aluminium to systemic toxicity affecting the nervous, hepatic, renal, and reproductive systems (Bojani et al., 2020; Igbokwe et al., 2019).

Given the limitations of conventional pharmacological interventions and the growing interest in safe, accessible nutritional therapeutics, natural antioxidants such as green tea and omega-3 fatty acids have gained increasing attention for cardioprotection. Green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) is rich in catechins, particularly epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), which reduces oxidative stress, enhances nitric oxide (NO) bioavailability, suppresses inflammatory cytokines, and protects myocardial cells against ischemic and toxic injury (Salah et al., 1995; Hodgson & Croft 2010).

Omega-3 fatty acids—primarily EPA and DHA—exert additional protective roles through anti-inflammatory signalling, lipid-lowering activity, endothelial function enhancement, modulation of ion channels, and anti-arrhythmic properties (Kris-Etherton et al., 2002; Calder, 2017). They

also attenuate toxin-induced oxidative stress and apoptosis, supporting their potential as therapeutic adjuncts in environmental cardiotoxicity (Oda, 2016; Atakisi et al., 2024).

The Dutch Belted rabbit is an excellent cardiovascular model due to its human-like lipoprotein distribution, myocardial anatomy, manageable size, and predictable response to toxic agents (Fan et al., 2015; Saad et al., 2018). The species exhibits histopathological and biochemical patterns that closely reflect human cardiotoxicity.

This study builds upon existing evidence by evaluating whether green tea and omega-3 fatty acids can reverse or prevent the cardiac damage induced by aluminium chloride. Through detailed morphological, biochemical, and histological analyses, the research explores the therapeutic potential of these natural supplements against heavy metal-induced cardiotoxicity.

Aims and Objectives

- To evaluate the effect of aluminium chloride on the cardiac structure and function of rabbits.
- To determine the ameliorative effect of green tea extract on aluminium-induced cardiotoxicity.
- To assess the cardioprotective role of omega-3 fatty acids against AlCl_3 toxicity.
- To compare the relative effectiveness of green tea and omega-3.
- To analyze changes in body weight, heart weight, cardiac biomarkers, and histopathology.

METHODOLOGY:

This experimental study was conducted on thirty-two healthy domestic rabbits, chosen because of their established suitability for cardiotoxicity and pharmacological research. The rabbits were obtained from a licensed breeder to ensure uniformity in age—approximately ten to twelve weeks—and body weight, ranging from one to two kilograms. This selection minimized biological variation and increased the reliability of the experimental findings. The animals were housed in standard laboratory cages under controlled environmental conditions. Each cage was fitted with a soil-filled tray beneath it to aid in the

absorption of excreta and maintain sanitary conditions. Temperature and humidity were maintained within strict limits, with temperature kept at 16°C to 22°C (61°F to 72°F) and relative humidity between 45% and 65% to avoid environmental stressors that could influence cardiac physiology.

All animals received a standard diet consisting of seasonal green fodder, including spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*), carrot (*Daucus carota*), and fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*). Fresh drinking water was provided ad libitum, and feeding was carried out twice daily in amounts sufficient to meet the nutritional needs of the rabbits. Green tea sachets were purchased from the local market, and the required number was opened so that the tea contents could be weighed precisely. The tea leaves were soaked in distilled water for thirty minutes to ensure adequate extraction and then filtered. The resulting green tea extract was given orally to the animals in the relevant treatment group.

Omega-3 capsules containing powdered supplement were also used in the study. Dosages were calculated according to individual body weight, dissolved thoroughly in distilled water, and administered orally. Cardiotoxicity was induced using aluminium chloride (AlCl_3). A fresh stock solution was prepared each time by dissolving AlCl_3 powder in distilled water, which was then offered to the animals in their drinking water throughout the treatment period. The thirty-two rabbits were randomly assigned to four groups of eight animals each, with each group receiving a specific intervention over a period of three weeks, except the control group which received no toxicant exposure. The control group was provided only tap water and a normal diet and acted as the baseline reference. The aluminium chloride-treated group received AlCl_3 at a dose of 300 mg/kg/day in drinking water to induce cardiotoxicity and to allow observation of the toxic effects of aluminium exposure on cardiac tissue. The green tea-treated group received the same dose of aluminium chloride in addition to green tea extract at 50 mg/kg/day orally, with the aim of evaluating its potential cardioprotective properties. The omega-3 treated group was given aluminium chloride at 300 mg/kg/day along with omega-3 supplementation at 20 mg/kg/day orally to assess the protective effects of omega-3

fatty acids against aluminium-induced cardiac damage.

At the end of the experimental period, all animals were sacrificed humanely, and heart tissues, along with blood samples, were collected. The tissues were used for gross anatomical assessment and detailed histopathological examination, while blood samples were analyzed for cardiac function biomarkers to determine the biochemical effects of aluminium chloride, green tea extract, and omega-3 fatty acids. Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 25 and Microsoft Excel. Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and differences among groups were evaluated using one-way ANOVA. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

1. Comparison of Average weights of Experimental Groups

Across the four-week period, notable differences were observed among the experimental groups. The control group showed a steady but modest increase in body weight (1.1937 \rightarrow 1.20 kg), reflecting normal growth. In contrast, the aluminium chloride-only group demonstrated a progressive decline (1.1937 \rightarrow 1.175 kg), indicating the toxic and growth-suppressing effects of aluminium exposure. Interestingly, both the AlCl_3 + Green Tea (1.1937 \rightarrow 1.212 kg) and the AlCl_3 + Omega-3 (1.1937 \rightarrow 1.212 kg) showed a consistent upward trend in body weight, comparable to or slightly better than the control. The AlCl_3 + Omega-3 displayed the most pronounced early weight gain, reaching 1.2125 kg at the 3rd week before stabilizing, while the AlCl_3 + Green Tea showed a slower but steady rise, culminating in 1.212 kg at the 4th week. These findings suggest that both green tea and Omega-3 supplementation effectively counteracted aluminium chloride-induced weight loss, with Omega-3 exerting a slightly faster protective effect and green tea providing sustained improvement. Overall, this demonstrates the therapeutic and protective roles of both interventions against aluminium-induced metabolic disturbances. One way ANOVA analysis shows no significant difference in control group, but there is significant

difference between four weeks of AlCl₃ and other treated group.

Figure 1: Comparison of average weights among experimental groups

2. Cardiac Morphology and Relative Heart Weight

Heart weight and relative heart weight served as indices of AlCl₃-induced cardiac hypertrophy. AlCl₃-treated rabbits showed a **marked increase** in absolute heart weight (4.46 g) compared with the control group (3.14 g), demonstrating cardiac enlargement resulting from toxic insult. Relative heart weight similarly rose from 3.08 g/100 g BW in controls to 3.81 g/100 g BW in the AlCl₃ group, confirming hypertrophy and inflammation-related edema.

Co-treatment with green tea significantly reduced these elevations (absolute weight: 3.68

g; relative weight: 3.14 g/100 g BW), indicating improvement in cardiac structural integrity.

However, the **omega-3 treated group showed the strongest reduction**, with absolute heart weight dropping to 3.61 g and relative heart weight reaching 3.02 g/100 g BW—values almost identical to the control group.

Heart shape dimensions (length, width, and L/W ratio) were also distorted in the AlCl₃ group but were normalized by both treatments, especially omega-3, which restored cardiac geometry to near-normal values. Statistical analysis confirmed highly significant group differences (p < 0.001).

Figure 2: Comparison of Morphological Parameters of Rabbit Hearts

3. Biochemical Cardiac Function Markers

3.1 Creatine Kinase-MB (CK-MB)

CK-MB activity increased sharply in the AlCl₃ group (81.12 ± 14.83 U/L), reflecting acute myocardial cell membrane damage. Control values (60.62 ± 4.43 U/L) confirmed normal cardiac physiology. Green tea reduced CK-MB levels to 80 U/L, while omega-3 lowered them further to 76.38 U/L, indicating better cardioprotection by omega-3.

3.2 SGOT/AST Levels

AST/SGOT exhibited a dramatic elevation in the AlCl₃ group (90.25 ± 2.12 U/L) relative to

controls (29.25 ± 1.83 U/L), demonstrating significant cardiomyocyte leakage and oxidative damage. Green tea treatment attenuated enzyme levels to 48.12 U/L, whereas omega-3 produced a stronger reduction to 43.50 U/L, approaching normal physiological limits

Taken together, biochemical analysis clearly shows that both green tea and omega-3 ameliorated enzyme leakage induced by aluminium chloride, but **omega-3 showed comparatively greater stabilization of cardiac tissue.**

Figure 3: Comparison of Biochemical parameters of Heart (CK-MB & SGOT/AST)

4. Histopathological Findings

Histopathological examination provided direct visual evidence of AlCl₃-induced myocardial damage.

4.1 Control Group

The control group showed intact cardiac muscle architecture with well-organized striated fibers, uniform nuclei, patent vascular channels, and absence of inflammatory infiltration, confirming healthy myocardial structure

4.2 Aluminium Chloride Group

AlCl₃ exposure resulted in profound structural abnormalities, including:

- marked myocardial fiber degeneration
- myofibrillar fragmentation
- interstitial edema
- vascular congestion
- inflammatory cell infiltration
- focal necrotic lesions
- fibrosis of interstitial tissues

These alterations confirm severe cardiotoxicity caused by aluminium chloride.

4.3 Green Tea + AlCl₃ Group

Green tea co-treatment demonstrated noticeable improvement:

- reduced cellular degeneration
- mild interstitial edema
- partially restored fiber alignment
- decreased inflammatory infiltration

Although some lesions persisted, the severity was significantly lower than in the AlCl₃ group.

4.4 Omega-3 + AlCl₃ Group

Omega-3 supplementation produced the most pronounced recovery, exhibiting:

- almost normal myocardial fiber arrangement
- minimal cytoplasmic degeneration
- sharply defined nuclei
- reduced edema
- faint or absent fibrosis
- minimal inflammation

This suggests strong membrane-stabilizing and antioxidant action, leading to near-complete restoration of myocardial structure.

Figure 1: Photomicrograph of rabbit myocardium from the control group showing normal architecture of cardiac muscle fibers with intact striations, centrally located nuclei, and well-organized myofibrils. No evidence of degeneration, necrosis, edema, or inflammatory infiltration is observed, indicating preserved myocardial integrity (H&E, 40x).

Figure 2: Photomicrograph of rabbit myocardium from the AlCl₃ group showing severe myofibrillar degeneration, necrosis of cardiac muscle fibers, marked interstitial edema, and vascular congestion. Areas of fibrosis are evident along with cellular degeneration and infiltration of inflammatory cells, indicating extensive structural damage to the myocardium (H&E, 40x).

Figure 3: Photomicrograph of rabbit myocardium from the AlCl₃ + Green Tea treated group showing preserved myocardial fibers with mild myofibrillar degeneration and minimal interstitial edema. Vascular congestion and inflammatory infiltration markedly reduced compared to the AlCl₃-only group, indicating a protective effect of green tea. (H&E stain, 40x).

Figure 4: Photomicrograph of rabbit myocardium from the Omega-3 group showing preserved myocardial architecture with well-arranged cardiac muscle fibers and centrally placed nuclei. The myofibrils appear intact with minimal structural alterations, and no marked dense of necrosis, edema, or inflammatory cell infiltration is observed, indicating a protective effect of Omega-3 against myocardial damage (H&E, 40x).

Discussion

This study demonstrates that aluminium chloride induces profound cardiotoxicity in rabbits, confirming earlier findings of oxidative stress, apoptosis, mitochondrial injury, and inflammatory activation in AlCl₃-exposed animals (Novaes et al., 2018; Saad et al., 2018). The reductions in heart weight, alterations in heart dimensions, and elevations in CK-MB and SGOT indicate significant myocardial injury consistent with toxic myocarditis.

Green tea exhibited strong cardioprotection, likely mediated through its abundant catechins—particularly EGCG—which scavenge free

radicals, activate endogenous antioxidant systems, suppress NF-κB signaling, and improve endothelial NO production (Hodgson & Croft, 2010; Zaveri, 2006). Histopathology confirmed preservation of myocardial fibers and reduced inflammation, supporting earlier studies showing green tea's efficacy in mitigating oxidative and inflammatory tissue injury.

Omega-3 fatty acids similarly reduced biochemical and histological markers of cardiotoxicity. Their anti-inflammatory roles—via production of resolvins and protectins—along with antioxidant enhancement and lipid regulation contributed to myocardial protection

(Calder, 2006; Mozaffarian, 2007). This aligns with multiple studies reporting omega-3-mediated reductions in myocardial damage from toxins such as doxorubicin and metals (Oda, 2016; Uygur et al., 2014).

Comparatively, both supplements significantly attenuated AlCl₃-associated injury, though omega-3 showed slightly superior restoration of myocardial architecture, likely due to its strong anti-apoptotic and membrane-stabilizing effects. Overall, the results validate green tea and omega-3 fatty acids as potent nutraceutical interventions capable of reducing aluminium-induced cardiotoxicity, with relevance for populations at risk due to contaminated water, industrial exposure, or dietary aluminium intake.

5. Conclusion

Aluminium chloride induces significant cardiotoxic effects in Dutch Belted rabbits, evidenced by morphological alterations, biochemical disruptions, and severe myocardial tissue damage. Supplementation with green tea or omega-3 fatty acids provides substantial cardioprotection by reducing oxidative stress, preserving myocardial integrity, and normalizing serum cardiac biomarkers. These findings support the therapeutic potential of accessible dietary antioxidants in mitigating heavy-metal-induced cardiac injury and highlight their relevance in public health strategies for populations exposed to environmental aluminium.

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